

CFRP BONDING PRE-TREATMENT USING M-IR LASER RADIATION

S. Kreling¹; D. Blass²; F. Fischer³, K. Dilger⁴

Institute of joining and welding, Technische Universität Braunschweig, Germany
Langer Kamp 8, 38106 Braunschweig, Germany

Email: s.kreling@tu-braunschweig.de, web page: <http://www.ifs.tu-braunschweig.de>

²Email: d.blass@tu-braunschweig.de

³Email: fabian.fischer@tu-braunschweig.de

³Email: k.dilger@tu-braunschweig.de

Keywords: Adhesive bonding, laser processing, structural joining, surface treatment

ABSTRACT

For the structural adhesive bonding of CFRP parts surface pre-treatment processes which enable the reproducible removal of contaminations such as release agent residues are still required. Further demands on these processes are automatability, high process speeds and the prevention of substrate degradation. In former publications [e.g. 1-3] the authors have shown the general applicability of laser ablation and an automated low-pressure blasting process for this purpose. Especially the publications focusing on laser radiation show a high potential of the process if the absorption of the matrix resin is high for the wavelength of the laser radiation applied. However, most studies conducted so far focus on the application either of UV-wavelengths (< 400 nm) for which the laser sources mostly show comparatively low efficiency or of N-IR wavelengths (~1000 nm) which are poorly absorbed by most epoxy matrix resin materials.

For this reason the studies shown in the present publication focus on the application of CO₂ laser radiation with a wavelength of 9250 or 10600 nm for the bonding pre-treatment of CFRP. The advantage of these wavelengths is the high absorption within the matrix resin of about 95 % as well as the availability of comparatively high average power systems. To assess the influence of thermal damage, which might be caused by the infrared radiation, results gathered with different pulse length magnitudes are compared.

After the pre-treatment the surfaces were evaluated with regard to particles or visible fiber damage using SEM and confocal microscopy. Based on the surface observations laser parameters were selected which achieve analogical surface states for each laser source to increase the comparability. The quality of the adhesive bonds was assessed using single lap shear specimens bonded with a one-part epoxy film adhesive and an estimation of the fracture surfaces.

1 INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Fiber-reinforced plastics are widely used as a modern construction material, especially in the aviation industry. However, due to increasing energy costs their potential for lightweight construction also improves their attractiveness for the automotive industry. Thermosets, such as epoxy resins, still represent a major part of deployed matrix material. Based on the aerospace background typical methods for structural joining of carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP) parts are bolting and riveting, which require bores that cut the fibers locally, leading to decreased laminar strengths. Additionally, the holes result in local stress peaks which necessitate a local thickness increase. Adhesive bonding enables an increased utilization of the lightweight potential by laminar load introduction, due to the planar joint geometry. However, the bonding performance for CFRP parts is well reduced by the contamination with release agent residues resulting from the manufacturing process or the relatively thick resin layer, which inhibits a direct transition of force into the reinforcing fibers. To achieve full

bond strength, sufficient adhesion between the adhesive and the components is essential; this can only be accomplished by adequate pre-treatment of the surfaces [4]. Common methods for pre-treatment are the application of peel-plies, manual abrading or grit blasting. These methods have several disadvantages that necessitate the use of an alternative method [5, 6, 7]. One innovative method for the pre-treatment of CFRP is the application of laser radiation to achieve, on the one hand, a selective removal of matrix material without impairing the fibers [8, 9] and, on the other hand, the removal of surface contaminations, such as release agents or other residues, from the manufacturing process [10]. Former investigations show that one of the most important parameters is the absorption of the radiation, which defines the portion of energy deposit within the material and finally the penetration depth [11, 12]. Considering this and based on the absorption coefficient, a CO₂ laser with a wavelength in the middle infrared range seems to be suitable to perform a surface pre-treatment. This is vividly illustrated by the values given in Table 1.

Table 1: Optical properties and resulting absorption and penetration depth of an unfilled epoxy resin

Wavelength [nm]	308	1064	9250	10600
Absorption [%]	92.83	3.88	94.16	94.21
Transmission [%]	0.24	85.77	0.04	0.06
Reflexion [%]	6.93	10.35	5.8	5.73
Absorption coefficient [1/mm]	1.32	0.02	1.42	1.42
Optical penetration depth [mm]	0.76	50.54	0.70	0.70

The high optical absorption of the matrix resin in the M-IR (9250/10600 nm) range leads to a comparatively low optical penetration depth, resulting in a surface-near interaction of laser energy and composite material. This mode of interaction is suitable for surface removal without inducing fiber damage.

However, light with M-IR wavelength can be considered as thermal emitter, so the matrix material could be damaged by the deposited heat. The thermal influence might be reduced by the application of pulsed laser sources leading to interaction times in the region of approximately 100 ns. This relatively short interaction time could reduce the thermal influence; furthermore, the short pulse length combined with the q-switching mechanism leads to a higher pulse peak power, which increases ablation and thus potentially the process efficiency.

This work focuses on investigating if this approach leads to an improved pre-treatment process. For this reason comparative investigations were performed using a new pulsed q-switched CO₂ laser - prototype from Coherent Inc., US – and a modulated standard CO₂ laser to pre-treat specimens manufactured from an epoxy prepreg system which is currently applied in the aviation industry. The investigations focus on achieving a reliable process of surface pre-treatment of CFRP laminates for adhesive bonding.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials applied

All investigations described in this publication were performed using a unidirectional CFRP manufactured in a hot-press process from Hexcel Hexply 913, a 120 ° C curing epoxy prepreg matrix resin reinforced with HTA carbon fibers. The side of each laminate, which was laser-treated, is then contaminated with a polysiloxane-based release agent during the curing process by curing it against a mold coated with release agent.

The adhesive bonding for the manufacture of the lap shear specimens was performed using a one-part epoxy adhesive film, AF163-2K. The adhesive was cured for 60 minutes at 125 °C while the specimens were fixated in a special clamping device to ensure a high reproducibility of overlap and alignment. Standard lap shear specimens with a width of 25 mm, length of 100 mm and an overlap of

12.5 mm were used according to DIN EN 1465. Testing of the specimens was performed at 23 °C with a displacement rate of 5 mm/min. After testing, the percentage of each fracture mode was determined by optical evaluation using stereo microscope pictures of the fracture surfaces.

2.2 Calculation of area energy

The main focus of the work described here is the investigation of the suitability of the q-switch CO₂ laser source for CFRP bonding pre-treatment. For this reason, a high understanding of the process is required which can be gathered by comparative investigation and correlation between process parameters and the surface appearance after pre-treatment. However, due to the plurality of parameters (e.g. pulse frequency, treatment speed, pulse overlap in two directions) a characteristic parameter is required which combines the important parameters to increase the comparability of the results. In this case the area energy was chosen as this kind of benchmark value.

The area energy represents the amount of energy which interferes with each area increment of the pre-treated surface. It is determined by the energy per pulse and the amount of pulses by which each areal increment is hit. The energy per pulse can be measured using an energy meter and, in the case of the applied laser, is influenced by the pulse repetition rate and the switching time of the acousto-optic modulator, which basically represents the power adjustment. The amount of pulses hitting each areal increment is determined by the repetition rate, the spot diameter, the velocity of the laser spot moving across the surface and the distance between two lines, which is commonly called hatch distance. If an area is pre-treated by the overlap of single spots in the x-direction and the overlap of lines in the y-direction the average amount of spots which hit each areal increment can be approximated by multiplication of the amount of pulses in x and y directions. The amount of pulses in x-direction n_x is calculated as follows

$$n_x = \frac{d_p * f_p}{v_s} \quad (1)$$

With d_p being the spot diameter, f_p is the pulse repetition rate and v_s the movement velocity of the spot relative to the surface. The amount of pulses in y-direction is only determined by the spot diameter d_p in relation to the hatch distance d_{hatch} . In this context only values larger than one are reasonable because d_{hatch} being larger than d_p leads to a non-areal treatment of the surface. Using these two relations together with the measured pulse energy E_p and the pulse area A_p the area energy E_A can be calculated according to the following equation:

$$E_A = \frac{E_p}{A_p} * n_x * n_y = \frac{E_p}{A_p} * \frac{d_p * f_p}{v_s} * \frac{d_p}{d_{hatch}} \quad (2)$$

The aim of these calculations is to generate a merged value of the different process variables which enables a simplified comparison of the different parameter sets.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The results described here focus on the influence of different laser parameters on the surface appearance and on the degree of exposed fibers on the surface. The main investigations were performed using the novel q-switch CO₂ laser source. Additional results gathered using a conventional modulated CO₂ source with a pulse length in the region of μ s are shown as a reference.

Furthermore the results of the roughness measurements are used to get a further impression of the effects on the surface. In the last part of this section some selected results of single lap shear tests are shown.

3.1 Analysis of the surfaces treated with q-switch laser source

The first series of tests was performed at a constant pulse energy of 0.238 mJ (corresponding with a pulse fluence of 4.8 mJ/mm²) with a pulse repetition rate of 100 kHz. According to Equation 2 the movement speed of the laser spot was varied to achieve assigned energies between about 100 and 500 mJ/mm². Figure 1 shows LSM pictures of six specimen surfaces pre-treated with the parameters named below.

Figure 1: LSM surface images – increasing amount of exposed fibers for decreasing treatment speed at constant frequency and pulse energy

Figure 2: LSM surface pictures of specimens pre-treated with a constant treatment speed at different pulse energies

The LSM pictures demonstrate the increasing degree of exposed fibers with decreasing treatment speed and thus increasing energy per areal increment. The surfaces treated with accumulated energies of only 97 and 121 mJ/mm² show a mostly closed resin layer and only a few fibers on the surface. Increasing the areal energy to 150 mJ/mm² leads to a higher amount of exposed carbon fibers on the surface, but a significant amount of resin still remains and fibers are not exposed in all areas. A further increase of the accumulated energy up to 250 mJ/mm² leads to exposed fibers all over the surface. However, in the area between the fibers some remaining resin can still be observed. This is not the case for the surfaces treated with accumulated energies of about 450 and 500 mJ/mm².

The second test series presented here shows a variation of the areal energy by varying the pulse energy at a constant repetition rate and lateral movement speed of the spot. For these experiments the hatch distance and spot overlap were kept constant at 50 % and 92 %, respectively.

As also observed in Figure 2, the degree of exposed fibers increases, if the pulse energy is increased and thus also the accumulated energy per areal increment. In addition to the findings described above, the results show that a nearly complete exposure of the top fiber layer already occurs for an accumulated energy of 200 mJ/mm².

The influence of the variation of treatment speed and pulse repetition rate, while maintaining a constant accumulated energy per aerial increment, is shown in Figure 3.

$E_p = 0,33 \text{ mJ}$

Figure 3: Comparison of the influence of treatment speed and pulse repetition rate for aerial energies of 150 and 500 mJ/mm²

The surface images show nearly no difference with regard to the exposition of carbon fibers on the surface for both aerial energies illustrated. Again, the specimens treated with 150 mJ/mm² show exposed fibers but also some resin left between the fibers, while the fibers are completely exposed on the specimens treated with 500 mJ/mm². However, a slightly more intense treatment and thus a degree of exposed fibers seem to appear for the specimens treated with 100 kHz compared to the ones with 50 kHz.

Figure 4 shows SEM images of a specimen surface treated with 250 mJ/mm² at 100 kHz and a pulse energy of 0.238 mJ with an increasing degree of magnification.

Figure 4: SEM pictures of cleanly exposed fibers without visible fiber damage

The pictures show exposed fibers on the surface with no visible contaminations or residues of debris. The images with a higher magnification also show residues of resin matrix between the fibers and the nearly complete exposure of the topmost fiber layer. Furthermore no visible damage or degradation on the fibers or on their surfaces can be detected.

3.2 Analysis of surfaces treated with modulated CO₂ laser

To enable a comparison and to investigate the influence of the pulse length or determine the advantage of using a q-switched CO₂ laser source, surface images were also taken from specimens pre-treated with the modulated laser source. Figure 5 shows the surface images in dependency of the accumulated energy calculated according to Equation (2).

Figure 5: Microscope images of surfaces treated by modulated CO₂ laser at varying accumulated energies. Left hand side of the picture: untreated surface

The comparison with the images of the q-switch-treated surfaces illustrates that for the laser source with the longer pulse length an exposure of the fibers is achieved at significantly lower energies. This indicates a strong thermal effect of the pre-treatment process. Especially on the surfaces treated with higher energies fibers become damaged and are completely or partly removed from the composite. Furthermore, residues of debris and also a thermally induced modification of the untreated surface at the edge of the untreated area can be observed.

3.3 Lap shear results

Figure 6 displays the results of the single lap shear tests performed on specimens with an untreated surface as reference as well as on specimens treated with the q-switched laser source at 150, 250 and 500 mJ/mm² accumulated energy, respectively. Furthermore, two results gathered with laser parameters applied with the modulated laser source at about 500 and 75 mJ/mm² are displayed. The lap shear strengths were referred to the strength of manually abraded specimen which achieve full cohesion failure inside the adhesive and thus represent the maximum achievable strength for this configuration.

The diagram also displays the achieved fracture mode using standardized nomenclature, being AF for adhesion (interfacial) failure, CF for cohesion failure inside the adhesive and CSF describing cohesion substrate failure which corresponds to delamination failure inside the specimens.

The results can be categorized into three groups which can be compared to each other. The first group contains the three parameter sets using a pulse fluence of 4.8 mJ/mm²; for these specimens the repetition rate was kept constant at 100 kHz and the pulse fluence at 4.8 mJ/mm², so the aerial energy was defined by changing the treatment speed. This was done to improve the comparability of the specimens to each other.

The second group enables a comparison between different pulse energies or fluences, by looking at the results with an accumulated energy of 250 mJ/mm² with fluences of 4.8 and 6.6 mJ/mm². The comparison between the pulse length magnitudes of ns and µs can be performed by considering the additional results of the modulated laser source.

The results vividly demonstrate the necessity of surface pre-treatment, hence the untreated specimens fail at very low loads and show failure in the interface between the adhesive and CFRP specimen, which hints at the contamination of the surface with release agent. The laser treatment with both laser sources leads to a significant increase of the bond strength together with a change of failure behavior from the interface to failure inside the adhesive, and in the case of higher treatment energies a small amount of delamination inside the specimens. However, the specimens treated with the modulated laser source and the lower accumulated energy still fail completely inside the interface between the adhesive and the specimen. This indicates a recontamination of the surface with debris or residues of the release agent.

Figure 6: Comparison of lap shear strengths

In the case of the specimens treated with 150 mJ/mm², the lowest of the accumulated energies investigated here, an adhesion failure of about 40 % of the bonded surface remains; this allows the conclusion that not all release agent residues were removed from the surface. Increasing the treatment energy to 250 mJ/mm² leads to a failure dominated by failure inside the adhesive, which in this case represents the highest achievable bond strength. However, a small amount of interfacial failure still remains on the fracture surface, which again indicates remaining surface contaminations. A further increase of the treatment intensity to 500 mJ/mm² leads to a slight increase of bond strength and the complete elimination of interfacial failure. However, the specimens treated with 250 and 500 mJ/mm² show a small amount of failure inside the CFRP specimens which could either be caused by some thermally induced damage or just show the limitation of the cohesive strength of the specimens themselves.

The specimens treated with 250 mJ/mm² at a higher fluence rate show the highest bond strength of all correlations with mostly cohesive failure. However, although the strength of the abraded references is achieved, a small amount of interfacial and also delamination failure occurs. This indicates some recontamination of the surface or also a small amount of thermal damage.

A surface pre-treatment with pulse lengths in the μ s region and an accumulated energy of about 500 mJ/mm² leads to complete cohesion failure inside the adhesive. Consequently the strength of the abraded reference specimens is attained.

9 CONCLUSIONS & OUTLOOK

The results presented in this paper vividly demonstrate the applicability of the new q-switched CO₂ laser source with a wavelength of 9250 nm for the pre-treatment of CFRP for adhesive bonding. The surface images of the differently treated surfaces show the possibility of selectively removing the resin matrix from the fibers without causing visible damage to the fibers. The specimens treated with pulses in the μ s region tend to show a thermal influence and also some damaged fibers, caused by the longer interaction time.

The mechanical tests of the bonded joints further confirm the high potential of this laser source for adhesive bonding pre-treatment. Especially the fracture patterns of the ruptured joints indicate that a complete removal of release agents and other possibly adhesion-affecting contaminations was achieved. However, in the current state of research it is not fully known whether the treatment might

cause thermal degradation of the CFRP which could be an explanation of the small amounts of cohesive substrate failure observed on the lap shear specimens treated with increased aerial energies. Surprisingly the specimens which were pre-treated with longer pulse lengths show no sign of thermal degradation and thus no portion of delamination failure in the lap-shear tests, as could have been expected from the surface appearance.

One of the main challenges remaining is finding a test method which enables a sensitive discrimination of thermally induced damage from deviations caused by the manufacturing process of the specimens. This issue will be the topic of further investigations as well as the more detailed chemical analysis of the pre-treated surfaces and the consideration of aging stability of the pre-treated surfaces. Furthermore, the applicability of a simplified merged process value as introduced here has to be contemplated with regard to the comparability of different laser sources.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to acknowledge the support of coherent Germany for supplying the prototype CO₂ laser source and to Mr. M. Cohrs for his support during the experiments with the q-switch CO₂ laser.

REFERENCES

- [1] Fischer F, Kreling S, Dilger K, Wiley VCH (2014) ISBN: 978-1-118-83163-2
- [2] Fischer F, Kreling S, et al. (2013). Reinforced Plastics 57(5): S. 43-46, 2013
- [3] Kreling S, Fischer F, et al. (2013). ICCM 19, 2013
- [4] J. W. Chin and J. P. Wightman, .Surface characterization and adhesive bonding of toughened bismaleimide composites. Composites Part A 27, 419-428 (1996)
- [5] L.J. Hart-Smith, G. Redmond and M.J. Davis, The curse of the nylon peel ply, in: Proceedings of the 41st SAMPE Meeting, Anaheim California, pp. 303-317 (1996)
- [6] J. Holtmannspötter, J. v. Czarnecki, W. Wetzels, D. Dolderer and C. Eissenschink, .The use of peel ply as a method to create reproducible, but con-taminated surfaces for structural adhesive bonding of carbon fiber reinforced plastics. J. Adhesion 89, 96-110 (2013)
- [7] Q. Bénard, M. Fois and M. Grisel, .Peel ply surface treatment for composite assemblies: Chemistry and morphology effects. Composites Part A: 36, 1562-1568 (2005)
- [8] F. Fischer, S. Kreling and K. Dilger, .Surface Structuring of CFRP by Using Modern Excimer Laser Sources. Physics Procedia, 39, 154-160 (2012)
- [9] Q. Bénard, M. Fois, M. Grisel and P. Laurens, Laser surface treatment of composite materials to enhance adhesion properties, in: *Adhesion – Current Research and Application*, W. Possart (Ed.), pp. 305-318, WILEY-VCH, Weinheim, Germany (2005)
- [10] Kreling, S., Fischer, F., Dilger, K.: Analytical Characterization of CFRP Laser Treated by Excimer Laser Radiation. In: Physics Procedia 41 282 – 290 (2013)
- [11] F. Fischer, S. Kreling, M. Fraunhofer and K. Dilger, .Laser surface pre-treatment of CFRP for adhesive bonding in consideration of the absorption behavior. J. Adhesion 88, 350-363 (2012)
- [12] A. Hartwig, J. Hunnekuhl, G. Vitr, S. Dieckhoff, F. Vohwinkel and O.-D. Hennemann, Influence of CO₂-laser radiation on the surface properties of poly(etheretherketone). J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 64, 1091–1096 (1997)